

The Microbond Test – Rubbish In = Rubbish Out?

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The Rubbish In, Rubbish Out Concept

- The **Rubbish In, Rubbish Out (RIRO)** concept is used in computer science and other fields to express the idea that, **incorrect or poor quality input** will always produce **faulty output**.
- Note: **RIRO** says nothing about the analysis method which may be flawless and work perfectly.

RIRO Applied to Experimental Research

**No matter how 'perfect' the test equipment,
a 'faulty' sample will give 'faulty' results**

Microbond Test for IFSS

Assuming shear stress is distributed uniformly around the interface then -

Average IFSS:

$$\tau = \frac{F_{\text{max}}}{A_e}$$

The Microbond Test

- **Note that the force is not applied directly to the interface in this test**
- **The applied force acts on the interface via the polymer “matrix”**
- **So it may be expected that polymer droplet properties will affect the results of the test**
- **So to screen for interface effects –**
 - **the droplet properties should not change from droplet to droplet in a single system**
 - **or from system to system if comparing interface effects between systems**

Microbond IFSS vs Polymer Modulus

How Big is a Microdroplet ?

Why Might Polymer Microdroplet Properties Differ From Expectations ?

- Crystalline structure of thermoplastics
- Polymer degradation effects
- Droplet morphology
- Moisture absorption
- Mixing effects
- Curing differences
- Evaporation of components
- Oxygen inhibition of cure
- Unexpected chemical interactions
- *...see.. Polymer Testing 111 (2022) 107591*

PP Droplet Degradation

10 12 15 20 30

PP47 - Minutes at 220°C

SEM of PP Microdroplets

How Many Spherulites in a Microdroplet ?

Moisture Absorption by Microdroplets

SEM of Epoxy Microdroplets

Curing Epoxy-Amine Microdroplets

VE Microdroplets vs Curing Atmosphere

Fibre Glue with VE Microdroplets

Some Conclusions

- The **Rubbish In, Rubbish Out** concept definitely applies to microbond test specimens.
- There are many reasons why properties of microbond droplets may be different from expectations
- The examples given here are just some of the issues discovered so far – there are probably many more
- This does not mean the microbond test is “faulty”
- However, users of the test need to be aware of these potential pitfalls when assigning further meaning or interpretation to their results.